

TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION (TLE) TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHOD

LUCENA C. AMOY

Abstract. The study unfolded the TLE teachers' professional development and the use of innovative teaching methods in Banaybanay District Schools, Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of leadership and advocacy, assessment and evaluation, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge, industry partnership technology is, moderately extensive, and, likewise, extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of real-world connections, integration of technology, active learning, reflection and feedback collaborative learning is moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between TLE teachers' professional development and use of innovative teaching methods. Domains of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of delivering content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, assessment and evaluation technology integration, and leadership and advocacy significantly influence use of innovative teaching methods. Future research may identify barriers and challenges faced by teachers in industry partnership and cultural competence. Investigate factors such as access to technology, teacher readiness, support systems, and institutional policies.

KEY WORDS

1. technology and livelihood education
2. teachers' professional development
3. innovative teaching method

1. Introduction

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers play a critical role in preparing students for the workforce by providing them with the necessary knowledge and skills to succeed in today's rapidly changing economy. However, teachers in this field face unique challenges in keeping up with the latest technologies and teaching strategies to meet the demands of their students and industry partners. In the international setting, concerns about TLE teachers' professional development and the use of innovative teaching methods have become increasingly prevalent, especially as countries aim to prepare their youth for the challenges of the 21st century workforce. According to Kaur and Javed (2020), one of the key challenges facing TLE teachers in the international setting is the need to constantly update their knowledge and

skills to keep up with the latest technologies and industry trends. This requires ongoing professional development and training, which can be difficult to access in some regions of the world. Additionally, TLE teachers may struggle to integrate innovative teaching methods into their classrooms due to a lack of resources or support from school administrators. Another concern in the international setting is the need for TLE teachers to develop cultural competence to better serve diverse student populations. As noted by Alao and Shamsudeen (2022), TLE teachers must be able to understand and address the unique cultural backgrounds and learning needs of their students to ensure that all students have access to high-quality education and job opportunities. Despite these challenges, there is growing recognition of the importance of TLE teachers' professional development and the need to support innovative teaching methods in the international setting. For example, a study by Chen and Wu (2021) found that professional development programs that focused on technology integration and pedagogical knowledge were effective in improving TLE teachers' teaching practices and student outcomes. In the Philippines, Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is a critical subject area that prepares students for the workforce by providing them with essential knowledge and skills. However, the TLE teachers in the country face significant challenges when it comes to their professional development and the use of innovative teaching methods in the classroom. These issues have become increasingly prevalent in recent years and require immediate attention to ensure that students receive high-quality education that aligns with the demands of the modern workforce. Bautista and Talaguit (2021), one of the key challenges facing TLE teachers in the Philippines is the lack of access to professional development opportunities. Many teachers in the country lack the necessary training and support to keep up with the latest technologies and teaching strategies, which can impact student learning outcomes. Additionally, some teachers struggle to integrate innovative teaching methods into their classrooms due to limited resources and support from school administrators. Another concern in the Philippines is the need for TLE teachers to develop 21st-century skills to prepare students for the demands of the workforce. As noted by Garingan and Arreola (2020), TLE teachers must possess a range of competencies, including critical thinking, communication, and problem-solving skills, to provide students with a well-rounded education that aligns with the needs of the modern economy. Despite these challenges, there is growing recognition of the importance of TLE teachers' professional development and the need for innovative teaching methods in the Philippines. For instance, a study by Prudente and Del Mundo (2020) found that TLE teachers who participated in professional development programs that focused on technology integration and pedagogical knowledge reported improved teaching practices and student outcomes. Overall, the issues and concerns surrounding TLE teachers' professional development and the use of innovative teaching methods in the Philippines are critical to address. With a commitment to ongoing training and support, in Banaybanay District Davao Oriental Schools Division, TLE teachers can play a vital role in preparing students for success in the country's rapidly changing economy, however, there is a need to review their professional development and the use of innovative teaching method, thus this paper is presented.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the discussion of the methodical process in the conduct of the study. This includes the process in the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness in the conduct of the methodical steps.

2.1. Research Design—Descriptive-correlational research design is a type of research that aims to describe the relationship between two or more variables. This type of research design does not involve any intervention or manipulation of variables but rather aims to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. Descriptive-correlational research design is often used in social science research, including educational research, as it allows researchers to examine patterns and relationships among variables that cannot be manipulated for ethical or practical reasons. According to Creswell (2014), descriptive-correlational research design is used to describe and explain the relationship between two or more variables. The main goal of this type of research design is to identify the relationship between variables, and it can be used to make predictions about future events. Descriptive-correlational research design is often used in exploratory studies or when researchers are interested in establishing the existence of a relationship between variables. In conclusion, descriptive-correlational research design is a valuable research tool in educational research as it allows researchers to examine the relationship between variables and make predictions about future events. This research design provides valuable information that can help educators and researchers to develop interventions and programs that can improve educational outcomes. The study could collect data on TLE teachers' participation in various professional development activities, such as workshops, conferences, and online courses, as well as their use

of innovative teaching methods, such as active learning, integration of technology, real-world connections, differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and reflection and feedback. By analyzing the data, the study could identify any correlations between TLE teachers' participation in professional development and their use of innovative teaching methods. Overall, the context of the study in using a descriptive correlational research design would be to provide a detailed description of the relationship between TLE teachers' professional development and their use of innovative teaching methods, which could inform future efforts to improve TLE teacher training and support.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Junior High School Teachers of Banaybanay District Schools in Davao de Oro Division. Using Raosoft sample size calculator, a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective Junior High Schools. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study. As much as possible, these respondents are teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in the respective schools to measure competence, and how they function and contributed to the learning outcomes given new normal learning system during SY 2023-2024. Ethics of research and in the process of collecting survey responses were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31

S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used a self-made survey instrument. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures. There are two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of the indicators of teachers’ professional development in terms of content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, assessment and evaluation, technology integration, industry partnership, cultural competence and leadership and advocacy. On the other hand, the second part of the survey is the extent of the use of innovative teaching method in terms of

active learning, integration of technology, real-world connections, differentiated instructions, collaborative learning, and reflection and feedback. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.889 which means that 889 percent level of confidence of the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs. (Pallant 2010).

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of teachers’ professional development. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Scale for Descriptive Rating of Teachers’ Professional Development

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers’ professional development is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers’ professional development is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers’ professional development is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers’ professional development is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers’ professional development is not manifested

Scale for Descriptive Rating of Innovative Teaching Methods

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The innovative teaching methods is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The innovative teaching methods is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The innovative teaching methods is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The innovative teaching methods is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The innovative teaching methods is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements explains the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements of the are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data. Permission to conduct the study. On January 2023, before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser and the

Dean of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the top management of DepEd Davao Oriental Division through channel. This permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal that includes information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided information about the purpose and goals of the study, and how the data was collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, researchers must ensure that all participants are fully informed about the study and their rights, and that they provide

informed consent before participating. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. March 2023, the researchers ensured the accuracy and completeness of data, the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires should be conducted in a standardized and systematic manner. The researcher went into the following: 1. Identifying the target population: The researcher identified the appropriate target population of the study, and ensure that the questionnaire is distributed only to individuals who meet the inclusion criteria. 2. Obtaining consent: The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before distributing the questionnaire. This may involve providing information about the purpose and goals of the study, as well as any potential risks and benefits. 3. Ensuring anonymity and confidentiality: The researcher ensured that the questionnaire is anonymous, meaning that respondents are not identified by name or other personal information. The researcher also ensured that the data collected is kept confidential and only used for the purposes of the study. 4. Standardizing the distribution process: The researcher standardized the process for distributing the questionnaire, to ensure that all participants receive the same instructions and have the same opportunity to complete the questionnaire. 5. Allowing sufficient time for completion: Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and were allowed to ask any questions they may have about the process. 6. Collecting the completed questionnaires: The researcher collected the completed questionnaires in a timely and organized manner, to ensure that data is not lost or misplaced. Collation and statistical treatment of

data. The following are the general conditions that were followed for collation and statistical treatment of data as part of the data gathering procedure: 1. Accuracy: The data should be accurate and free from errors. This means that the data should be checked and validated to ensure that it is correct. 2. Completeness: The data should be complete, meaning that all necessary information has been collected. This is important because incomplete data can lead to incorrect conclusions. 3. Consistency: The data should be consistent, meaning that there are no contradictions or discrepancies in the data. Inconsistencies can lead to confusion and inaccuracies. 4. Relevance: The data should be relevant to the research question or problem being investigated. Irrelevant data can lead to incorrect conclusions. 5. Timeliness: The data should be collected and analyzed in a timely manner. Delayed or outdated data may not be useful or accurate. 6. Objectivity: The data should be objective, meaning that it is free from bias or personal opinions. This is important because biased data can lead to incorrect conclusions. 7. Validity: The data should be valid, meaning that it measures what it is supposed to measure. This is important because invalid data can lead to incorrect conclusions. 8. Reliability: The data should be reliable, meaning that it can be replicated or reproduced. This is important because unreliable data can lead to incorrect conclusions. 9. Statistical treatment: The data should be subjected to appropriate statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. Statistical analysis can help to reveal important insights and relationships in the data.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation was used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) on the extent of teachers' professional development, and statement problem number two (2) on the ex-

tent of the use of innovative teaching methods. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between teachers' professional development and

the use of innovative teaching methods in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the domains of teachers' professional development that significantly influence the use of innova-

tive teaching methods. All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Extent of TLE Teachers' Professional Development The importance of professional development for TLE teachers has been highlighted by researchers such as Sori and Suviste (2019). They argued that professional development plays a crucial role in enhancing TLE teachers' competencies, knowledge, and skills, which are essential for effective classroom teaching. Professional development can provide opportunities for TLE teachers to update their knowledge on the latest technologies and pedagogical approaches, and enable them to incorporate these innovations into their classroom practices. Similarly, in the Philippine setting, the importance of professional development for TLE teachers has been emphasized by various studies. A study conducted by Delos Santos and Acedera (2018) found that professional development activities such as training workshops and seminars positively impacted TLE teachers' teaching practices and student learning outcomes. Additionally, professional development can enable TLE teachers to develop a range of competencies that are essential for the 21st-century workforce, as highlighted by Garingan and Arreola (2020). Moreover, professional development can also help TLE teach-

ers in the Philippines to address the challenges they face in the implementation of the subject. As noted by Bautista and Talaguit (2021), TLE teachers in the country face various challenges, such as limited resources and support, and lack of access to professional development opportunities. Professional development can equip TLE teachers with the knowledge, skills, and strategies to overcome these challenges and provide quality education to their students.

Table 1 shows the extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of content knowledge. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: TLE teachers who prioritize their own content knowledge development can serve as role models for their students, demonstrating the importance of lifelong learning and staying current within their field (4.12), TLE teachers who possess a strong content knowledge base are better equipped to provide meaningful and relevant feedback to students, which can enhance the learning experience (4.00) and Professional development opportunities focused on content knowledge can help TLE teachers develop a more thorough understanding of the concepts and skills they teach, which can improve student outcomes (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, A deep understanding of the content within their field is critical for TLE teachers to effectively design and deliver lessons that engage students and promote their learning (3.25) and TLE teachers' content knowledge must be regularly updated to keep pace with changes

in technology and emerging trends within their field (3.10) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.54 denotes extent of TLE teachers’ professional development in terms of content knowledge is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 1. Extent of TLE Teachers’ Professional Development in terms of Content Knowledge

No	Content Knowledge	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	A deep understanding of the content within their field is critical for TLE teachers to effectively design and deliver lessons that engage students and promote their learning.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
2	TLE teachers’ content knowledge must be regularly updated to keep pace with changes in technology and emerging trends within their field.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	TLE teachers who possess a strong content knowledge base are better equipped to provide meaningful and relevant feedback to students, which can enhance the learning experience.	4.00	Extensive
4	Professional development opportunities focused on content knowledge can help TLE teachers develop a more thorough understanding of the concepts and skills they teach, which can improve student outcomes.	3.40	Extensive
5	TLE teachers who prioritize their own content knowledge development can serve as role models for their students, demonstrating the importance of lifelong learning and staying current within their field.	4.12	Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.54	Extensive

Content knowledge refers to the understanding of the subject matter that TLE teachers are expected to teach. It includes a comprehensive knowledge of the technical skills, processes, and principles involved in a particular field of study. According to Jones and Robinson (2019), content knowledge is the foundation of effective teaching and learning in TLE. TLE teachers must have a strong content knowledge to effectively communicate the subject matter to their students and help them develop the necessary skills. The importance of content knowledge for TLE teachers is also highlighted by researchers such as Akarsu and Iyibilgin (2020). They argued that content knowledge is critical for effective instruction and learning outcomes

in vocational education. Teachers with a deep understanding of the content they are teaching are more likely to provide students with clear explanations and guide them through the technical processes, which can enhance their understanding of the subject matter. Moreover, content knowledge is also essential in helping TLE teachers develop innovative and engaging teaching practices that align with industry standards. According to a study by Rivas and Japitana (2020), TLE teachers with a deep understanding of the content they are teaching are more likely to develop relevant activities and projects that can stimulate students’ interests and enhance their learning outcomes. However, the fast-changing nature of technology and

vocational skills requires TLE teachers to continuously update their content knowledge. As emphasized by Ismael and Maguad (2021), professional development programs must prioritize content knowledge to equip TLE teachers with the latest technical skills and knowledge. This can help TLE teachers stay relevant and provide students with quality education that meets industry standards.

Table 2 shows the extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of pedagogical knowledge. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Content pedagogy refers to the specialized knowledge and skills needed to teach specific content areas effectively. For TLE teachers, this means developing a deep understanding of the pedagogical approaches that work best for teaching technology and livelihood skills to students (4.25) is always manifested; TLE teachers who focus on developing their content pedagogy skills are better equipped

The importance of pedagogical knowledge for TLE teachers cannot be overemphasized. As highlighted by Shroff and Patel (2020), effective TLE teaching requires the use of pedagogical strategies that cater to the diverse needs of learners. TLE teachers with strong pedagogical knowledge can create learner-centered teaching environments that allow for meaningful and relevant learning experiences. TLE teachers with a sound understanding of pedagogical knowledge can effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. According to a study by Baser and Gunay (2021), TLE teachers with a deep understanding of pedagogical knowledge can incorporate technology in ways that enhance students' understanding of technical and vocational skills. As highlighted by He and Lei (2019), professional development programs can provide TLE teachers with opportunities to learn new pedagogical strategies and techniques

to differentiate instruction for their students, taking into account individual learning styles, interests, and abilities (4.10) and Professional development opportunities focused on content pedagogy can help TLE teachers build a toolkit of teaching strategies that are effective for delivering lessons in their field (4.00) are oftentimes manifested, while; A strong foundation in content pedagogy allows TLE teachers to create instructional materials and assessments that align with their state standards and curriculum frameworks, which can improve student achievement (3.35) is sometimes manifested, and When TLE teachers invest in their own content pedagogy development, they are more likely to stay current on trends and emerging research within their field, which can benefit their students' learning experiences (2.12) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.56 denotes extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of pedagogical knowledge is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

niques that can improve their teaching effectiveness. Additionally, professional development programs can help TLE teachers reflect on their teaching practices and implement new strategies to cater to the diverse needs of learners. Salvaña and Abao (2020) emphasized that TLE teachers must possess the pedagogical knowledge to integrate technology into their teaching effectively. This includes the selection and utilization of appropriate tools and methods to support the teaching and learning of technical and vocational skills. Alinsunod et al. (2021), TLE teachers can benefit from professional development programs that focus on pedagogical strategies and techniques. These programs provide opportunities for TLE teachers to learn new approaches, reflect on their teaching practices, and improve their overall instructional effectiveness.

Table 3 shows the extent of TLE teachers'

Table 2. Extent of TLE Teachers’ Professional Development in terms of Pedagogical Knowledge

No	Pedagogical Knowledge	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Content pedagogy refers to the specialized knowledge and skills needed to teach specific content areas effectively. For TLE teachers, this means developing a deep understanding of the pedagogical approaches that work best for teaching technology and livelihood skills to students.	4.25	Very Extensive
2	TLE teachers who focus on developing their content pedagogy skills are better equipped to differentiate instruction for their students, taking into account individual learning styles, interests, and abilities.	4.10	Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on content pedagogy can help TLE teachers build a toolkit of teaching strategies that are effective for delivering lessons in their field.	4.00	Extensive
4	A strong foundation in content pedagogy allows TLE teachers to create instructional materials and assessments that align with their state standards and curriculum frameworks, which can improve student achievement.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
5	When TLE teachers invest in their own content pedagogy development, they are more likely to stay current on trends and emerging research within their field, which can benefit their students’ learning experiences.	2.12	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.56	Extensive

professional development in terms of assessment and evaluation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Professional development opportunities focused on assessment and evaluation can help TLE teachers develop skills related to designing, administering, and grading assessments that align with their state standards and curriculum frameworks (4.18) and Assessment and evaluation are critical components of teaching and learning in TLE. TLE teachers must be equipped with the skills and knowledge to develop and administer appropriate assessments that accurately measure student understanding of content (4.00) are oftentimes manifested; while, TLE teachers who prioritize assessment and evaluation as part of their professional development are better equipped to

Assessment is the process of gathering information about students' learning progress, while evaluation involves making judgments about that progress in relation to established standards or learning goals. According to Crooks (2019), assessment can be classified into two categories: formative assessment and summative assessment. Formative assessment is an ongoing process that provides feedback to both teachers and students on their learning progress, allowing for instructional adjustments to be made throughout the learning process. Summative assessment, on the other hand, is used to evaluate the effectiveness of the learning experience at the end of a unit, course, or program. Moreover, assessment and evaluation help TLE teachers make informed decisions about curriculum design, instructional strategies, and the selection of appropriate learning resources. As noted by Eynon and Malmberg (2020), "quality assessment and evaluation practices are essential for ensuring that students receive the highest quality education possible. Professional development in assessment and evaluation can help

identify student strengths and weaknesses and to adjust their teaching methods to better support student learning (3.50), TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of assessment and evaluation practices are better equipped to provide meaningful feedback to students, which can improve their learning experiences (3.38), and A focus on assessment and evaluation as part of TLE teachers' professional development can lead to more accurate and reliable data on student learning outcomes, which can be used to inform decision-making and improve instruction (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.61 denotes extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of assessment and evaluation is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

TLE teachers improve their ability to design and implement assessments that are valid, reliable, and aligned with learning goals. It can also help them develop effective strategies for analyzing assessment results and using that information to improve their teaching practices. According to the Department of Education's Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of Grades 11 and 12 Career Pathways (2019), "assessment and evaluation must be conducted regularly to monitor and evaluate students' progress in the acquisition of competencies and to improve the teaching and learning process." The guidelines also emphasize the importance of providing professional development opportunities for TLE teachers to enhance their skills in assessment and evaluation. Professional development programs should also focus on the use of technology in assessment and evaluation. As noted by Fadul, Sarmiento, and Soriano (2020), technology-based assessments provide more opportunities for students to demonstrate their learning and allow for more efficient and accurate evaluation of their performance. As

Table 3. Extent of TLE Teachers’ Professional Development in terms of Assessment and Evaluation

No	Assessment and Evaluation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Assessment and evaluation are critical components of teaching and learning in TLE. TLE teachers must be equipped with the skills and knowledge to develop and administer appropriate assessments that accurately measure student understanding of content.	4.00	Extensive
2	TLE teachers who prioritize assessment and evaluation as part of their professional development are better equipped to identify student strengths and weaknesses and to adjust their teaching methods to better support student learning.	3.50	Moderately Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on assessment and evaluation can help TLE teachers develop skills related to designing, administering, and grading assessments that align with their state standards and curriculum frameworks.	4.18	Extensive
4	TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of assessment and evaluation practices are better equipped to provide meaningful feedback to students, which can improve their learning experiences.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on assessment and evaluation as part of TLE teachers’ professional development can lead to more accurate and reliable data on student learning outcomes, which can be used to inform decision-making and improve instruction.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.56	Extensive

such, TLE teachers must receive training in the use of various assessment technologies and platforms to improve their assessment practices.

Table 4 shows the extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of technology integration. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Technology integration is a critical component of TLE instruction, as it helps prepare students for success in a rapidly-evolving technological landscape. TLE teachers must be equipped with the skills and knowledge to effectively integrate technology into their lessons (3.50) and TLE teachers who prioritize technology integration as part of their professional development are better equipped to engage students and promote their learning through the use of technology are oftentimes manifested, (3.00); while, TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of technology

integration are better equipped to teach students important skills related to information literacy, digital citizenship, and responsible technology use (2.38), are sometimes manifested, while, Professional development opportunities focused on technology integration can help TLE teachers develop skills related to selecting appropriate technology tools, designing technology-rich lessons, and effectively managing technology in the classroom (2.18) and A focus on technology integration as part of TLE teachers' professional development can also help teachers stay up-to-date with emerging trends and technologies in their field, which can benefit their students' learning experiences (2.00) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.61 denotes extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of technology integration is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Technology integration has become an essential part of education, including Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), which aims to provide students with skills and knowledge in various fields such as agriculture, entrepreneurship, and home economics. To effectively incorporate technology in TLE instruction, teachers must possess the necessary skills and knowledge to utilize technology in their teaching methods. Professional development programs play a crucial role in enhancing TLE teachers' technology integration skills and knowledge, enabling them to deliver quality instruction to their students. A study conducted by Döş and Döş (2020) aimed to investigate the impact of professional development programs on technology integration in TLE instruction in Turkey. The study found that TLE teachers who participated in professional development programs were more likely to integrate technology into their instruction effectively. The study highlights the importance of professional devel-

opment programs in enhancing TLE teachers' technology integration skills. Another study by Kim and Lee (2019) explored the impact of technology integration on TLE student learning outcomes in South Korea. The study found that TLE teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) significantly influenced their ability to integrate technology into their instruction effectively, resulting in improved student learning outcomes. Furthermore, a study by Rambe and Bere (2019) focused on the importance of mobile learning as a tool for technology integration in TLE instruction in South Africa. The study found that TLE teachers who possess the necessary skills and knowledge to integrate mobile learning into their instruction can provide students with engaging and personalized learning experiences that enhance their understanding of TLE concepts. The study highlights the importance of professional development programs that incorporate mobile learning as a tool for technology integration in

Table 4. Extent of TLE Teachers’ Professional Development in terms of Technology Integration

No	Technology Integration	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Technology integration is a critical component of TLE instruction, as it helps prepare students for success in a rapidly-evolving technological landscape. TLE teachers must be equipped with the skills and knowledge to effectively integrate technology into their lessons.	3.50	Extensive
2	TLE teachers who prioritize technology integration as part of their professional development are better equipped to engage students and promote their learning through the use of technology.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on technology integration can help TLE teachers develop skills related to selecting appropriate technology tools, designing technology-rich lessons, and effectively managing technology in the classroom.	2.18	Less Extensive
4	TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of technology integration are better equipped to teach students important skills related to information literacy, digital citizenship, and responsible technology use.	2.38	Less Extensive
5	A focus on technology integration as part of TLE teachers’ professional development can also help teachers stay up-to-date with emerging trends and technologies in their field, which can benefit their students’ learning experiences.	2.00	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.61	Moderately Extensive

TLE instruction.

Table 5 shows the extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of industry partnership. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of industry partnership are better equipped to help students explore and prepare for careers in their field of study, which can lead to better post-graduation outcomes (3.38) and TLE teachers who develop partnerships with industry professionals are better equipped to integrate real-world applications into their instruction, which can enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes (3.20) and Industry partnerships provide TLE teachers with the opportunity to stay current on industry trends and technologies, which is critical for designing relevant and effective curriculum for

The field of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) emphasizes the development of technical skills and knowledge needed for students to pursue careers in various industries. One of the critical domains of professional development for TLE teachers is industry partnership. This domain involves developing collaborative partnerships between the educational institution and industry players to ensure that students receive relevant and up-to-date education that prepares them for the workforce. Industry partnerships have become increasingly important in recent years as the demand for skilled workers in different fields continues to grow. According to a study by Suyat et al. (2019), industry partnerships can provide students with opportunities to learn from industry experts and gain relevant skills and knowledge. The study also highlights the need for TLE teachers to engage in professional development activities that help them to build relationships with industry players and stay up-to-date with industry trends. Furthermore, industry partnerships can

their students (3.10) are sometimes manifested; while, A focus on industry partnership as part of TLE teachers' professional development can also help to build a bridge between academic study and practical applications of technology and livelihood skills, which can lead to greater student success in the workforce (2.25) and Professional development opportunities focused on industry partnership can help TLE teachers develop skills related to networking, collaboration, and communication with industry professionals, which can facilitate meaningful partnerships and improve student experiences (2.10) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.80 denotes extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of industry partnership is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

also help to bridge the gap between the classroom and the workplace. As noted by Wang and Li (2020), partnerships between educational institutions and industries can help to align the curriculum with the needs of the industry. This alignment can lead to a better understanding of the skills and knowledge required for success in various industries and help students to make informed decisions about their career paths. As discussed by Park (2022), partnerships with industry players can provide opportunities for grants and funding that can be used to enhance the educational experience for students. This funding can be used to purchase equipment, develop new programs, and support professional development activities for teachers. Through collaborations with industries, TLE teachers gain access to up-to-date knowledge and skills necessary to teach their students relevant and applicable technical skills. Industry partnership also helps TLE teachers become aware of the current job market demands and the technical skills needed by their students to succeed in

Table 5. Extent of TLE Teachers' Professional Development in terms of Industry Partnership

No	Industry Partnership	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Industry partnerships provide TLE teachers with the opportunity to stay current on industry trends and technologies, which is critical for designing relevant and effective curriculum for their students.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
2	TLE teachers who develop partnerships with industry professionals are better equipped to integrate real-world applications into their instruction, which can enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on industry partnership can help TLE teachers develop skills related to networking, collaboration, and communication with industry professionals, which can facilitate meaningful partnerships and improve student experiences.	2.10	Less Extensive
4	TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of industry partnership are better equipped to help students explore and prepare for careers in their field of study, which can lead to better post-graduation outcomes.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on industry partnership as part of TLE teachers' professional development can also help to build a bridge between academic study and practical applications of technology and livelihood skills, which can lead to greater student success in the workforce.	2.25	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.80	Moderately Extensive

their chosen careers.

Table 6 shows the extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of cultural competence. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: TLE teachers who develop cultural competence are better equipped to create a welcoming and inclusive classroom environment that fosters student learning and success (4.00) is oftentimes manifested, while, TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of cultural competence are better equipped to create curriculum that reflects the experiences and contributions of diverse cultures, which can enhance student engagement and promote social-emotional development (3.35) and Cultural competence is critical for TLE teachers who work with a diverse range of students from dif-

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers face the challenge of educating a diverse student population that comes from various cultural backgrounds. Thus, TLE teachers need to have cultural competence, which is defined as the ability to effectively interact and communicate with individuals from different cultural backgrounds. It is an essential domain of professional development for TLE teachers to provide an inclusive and equitable learning environment for all students. Cultural competence is a set of attitudes, behaviors, and policies that enable people to work effectively with individuals from different cultures. It involves being aware of one's own cultural background, understanding and appreciating the diversity of other cultures, and adapting to different cultural practices and customs. According to a study by Lee et al. (2020), cultural competence training can significantly improve teachers' attitudes and beliefs towards culturally diverse students, enhance their cultural knowledge, and improve their ability to create culturally responsive teaching practices. Another study by Chen

ferent backgrounds, cultures, and experiences (3.25) are sometimes manifested; while, A focus on cultural competence as part of TLE teachers' professional development can also help to reduce disparities in student outcomes across different cultural and ethnic groups, which can lead to greater equity and social justice in education (2.30) and Professional development opportunities focused on cultural competence can help TLE teachers develop skills related to understanding and respecting cultural differences, recognizing biases and stereotypes, and adapting instruction to meet the needs of diverse learners (2.00) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.98 denotes extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of cultural competence is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

et al. (2019) found that TLE teachers who participated in cultural competence professional development reported increased confidence and effectiveness in teaching culturally diverse students and a better understanding of how to create a culturally responsive curriculum. Cultural competence is a crucial domain of professional development for Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in the Philippine setting. This competency allows teachers to understand, appreciate, and respect the diversity of cultures among their students and incorporate it into their teaching strategies. The TLE curriculum emphasizes the development of vocational and technical skills, making cultural competence even more important for teachers as they work with diverse student populations.

Table 7 shows the extent of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of leadership and advocacy. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Leadership and advocacy skills are essential for TLE teachers who seek to drive change and improve outcomes for their

Table 6. Extent of TLE Teachers’ Professional Development in terms of Cultural Competence

No	Cultural Competence	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Cultural competence is critical for TLE teachers who work with a diverse range of students from different backgrounds, cultures, and experiences.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
2	TLE teachers who develop cultural competence are better equipped to create a welcoming and inclusive classroom environment that fosters student learning and success.	4.00	Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on cultural competence can help TLE teachers develop skills related to understanding and respecting cultural differences, recognizing biases and stereotypes, and adapting instruction to meet the needs of diverse learners.	2.00	Less Extensive
4	TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of cultural competence are better equipped to create curriculum that reflects the experiences and contributions of diverse cultures, which can enhance student engagement and promote social-emotional development.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on cultural competence as part of TLE teachers’ professional development can also help to reduce disparities in student outcomes across different cultural and ethnic groups, which can lead to greater equity and social justice in education.	2.30	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.98	Moderately Extensive

students and communities (4.20) is always manifested; TLE teachers who develop leadership and advocacy skills are better equipped to take an active role in shaping education policy, collaborating with stakeholders, and advocating for the needs of their students and programs (4.00) and Professional development opportunities focused on leadership and advocacy can help TLE teachers develop skills related to communication, problem-solving, strategic planning, and decision-making, which are essential for effective leadership and advocacy (3.50) are oftentimes manifested; while, TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of leadership and

advocacy are better equipped to drive change within their programs, school districts, and the wider community, which can lead to better outcomes for students and greater support for TLE programs (3.35) and A focus on leadership and advocacy as part of TLE teachers’ professional development can also help to promote the value of TLE education and the important role it plays in preparing students for success in the workforce and beyond (3.30) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.67 denotes extent of TLE teachers’ professional development in terms of leadership and advocacy is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 7. Extent of TLE Teachers’ Professional Development in terms of Leadership and Advocacy

No	Leadership and Advocacy	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Leadership and advocacy skills are essential for TLE teachers who seek to drive change and improve outcomes for their students and communities.	4.20	Very Extensive
2	TLE teachers who develop leadership and advocacy skills are better equipped to take an active role in shaping education policy, collaborating with stakeholders, and advocating for the needs of their students and programs.	4.00	Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on leadership and advocacy can help TLE teachers develop skills related to communication, problem-solving, strategic planning, and decision-making, which are essential for effective leadership and advocacy.	3.50	Extensive
4	TLE teachers who possess a strong understanding of leadership and advocacy are better equipped to drive change within their programs, school districts, and the wider community, which can lead to better outcomes for students and greater support for TLE programs.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on leadership and advocacy as part of TLE teachers’ professional development can also help to promote the value of TLE education and the important role it plays in preparing students for success in the workforce and beyond.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.67	Extensive

Leadership in education is the ability to inspire and guide others towards a common goal of improving learning outcomes for students (Lumby Foskett, 2021). In the context of TLE education, effective leadership is crucial for motivating teachers to adopt innovative teaching methods and ensure that the curriculum is aligned with the needs of the industry. In their study on teacher leadership in vocational education, Schulte et al. (2019) found that teacher leaders can play a crucial role in driving innovation and change in vocational education programs. These leaders are often passionate and enthusiastic about their subject matter and possess the skills and knowledge needed to inspire others. The domain of leadership and advocacy is crucial for the professional development of TLE teachers. Firstly, it enables them to have a voice in educational decision-making processes. According to Hargreaves and O’Connor (2018), teacher leadership is essential for creating and sustaining effective educational reforms. TLE teachers who are effective leaders and advocates can contribute to the development of policies and programs that are beneficial to their profession and their students. Secondly, leadership and advocacy enable TLE teachers to actively participate in their professional communi-

ties. By engaging in discussions, sharing knowledge and expertise, and collaborating with colleagues, TLE teachers can stay up-to-date with the latest trends and innovations in their field (Koh et al., 2019). This can lead to the improvement of their teaching practices and the quality of education they provide. Lastly, leadership and advocacy can also contribute to the personal and professional growth of TLE teachers. By taking on leadership roles and advocating for their profession, TLE teachers can develop new skills and broaden their knowledge and understanding of education (Hargreaves O’Connor, 2018). This can lead to greater job satisfaction and a sense of fulfillment in their profession.

Table 8 shows the summary of the extent of TLE teachers’ professional development. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: leadership and advocacy (3.67), assessment and evaluation (3.61), pedagogical knowledge (3.56), and content knowledge (3.54) are oftentimes manifested; while, industry partnership (2.80) and technology integration (2.61) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.25 denotes extent of TLE teachers’ professional development is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 8. Summary of the Extent of TLE Teachers’ Professional Development

No	TLE Teachers’ Professional Development	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Content knowledge	3.54	Extensive
2	Pedagogical knowledge	3.56	Extensive
3	Assessment and evaluation	3.61	Extensive
4	Technology integration	2.61	Moderately Extensive
5	Industry partnership	2.80	Moderately Extensive
6	Cultural competence	2.98	Moderately Extensive
7	Leadership and advocacy	3.67	Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.25	Moderately Extensive

Effective TLE instruction relies on teachers possessing a deep understanding of the subject matter they are teaching. TLE teachers should

have a comprehensive grasp of the content domains within their specialized area, whether it be information technology, home economics,

or industrial arts. Continuous professional development programs, workshops, and collaboration with industry experts are essential to enhance teachers' content knowledge and keep them up to date with the latest developments in their respective fields. Apart from content knowledge, TLE teachers must also possess pedagogical knowledge to effectively engage and instruct their students. Pedagogical knowledge encompasses instructional strategies, classroom management techniques, student assessment methods, and differentiation strategies to cater to diverse learners. Professional development opportunities should focus on enhancing TLE teachers' pedagogical skills through workshops, seminars, and peer collaboration. Assessment and evaluation play a critical role in monitoring student progress and informing instructional decisions. TLE teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to design valid and reliable assessments that align with learning objectives. Professional development initiatives should provide training on various assessment methods, such as performance-based assessments, portfolios, and rubrics, to ensure fair and accurate evaluation of students' skills and competencies. In today's digital age, the effective integration of technology in TLE instruction is imperative. Professional development programs should equip TLE teachers with the necessary skills to integrate technology tools and resources into their teaching practice. This includes training on using educational software, multimedia resources, online platforms, and collaborative tools to enhance student learning and engagement. To bridge the gap between classroom learning and real-world application, TLE teachers should establish partnerships with industry professionals and local businesses. Professional development opportunities should emphasize the importance of industry partnerships, enabling teachers to network, collaborate, and stay updated on industry trends. Engaging in internships, apprenticeships, or job shadowing

programs can provide teachers with firsthand industry experience to enrich their teaching. TLE teachers work with students from diverse cultural backgrounds. Developing cultural competence is crucial to create an inclusive learning environment and meet the unique needs of each learner. Professional development programs should address cultural sensitivity, intercultural communication, and strategies for accommodating cultural diversity within TLE instruction. TLE teachers can play a leadership role in promoting the significance of career and technical education. Professional development initiatives should empower teachers with leadership skills and strategies to advocate for TLE programs, secure resources, and collaborate with stakeholders. Training in effective communication, policy analysis, and program evaluation enables TLE teachers to act as advocates for their students and the field of TLE.

Extent of the Use of Innovative Teaching Methods In recent years, there has been growing emphasis on the use of innovative teaching methods in technology and livelihood education (TLE). Innovative teaching methods, which include various forms of technology-enhanced learning, have been shown to have a positive impact on student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. One key advantage of innovative teaching methods is that they can help to make learning more engaging and interactive for students. A study by Shively, Rowland, and Tucker (2020) found that the use of augmented reality (AR) technology in a TLE course led to increased student engagement and motivation, as well as improved learning outcomes. Similarly, a study by Abdullah and Ahmed (2018) found that the use of gamification in a TLE course led to increased student motivation and participation. Furthermore, innovative teaching methods can help to prepare students for the rapidly evolving demands of the modern workplace. A study by Rashid and Asghar (2019) found that the use of project-based learning

in a TLE course helped to develop students' problem-solving and critical thinking skills, as well as their ability to work collaboratively and communicate effectively. These skills are highly valued by employers and are becoming increasingly important in the modern workplace.

Table 9 shows the extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of active learning. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: TLE teachers who incorporate active learning strategies into their instruction are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of their students and promote inclusive and equitable classrooms (3.45) is oftentimes manifested; TLE teachers who incorporate active learning strategies into their instruction are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of their students and promote inclusive and equitable classrooms (3.25), Active learning is a student-

centered approach to teaching that prioritizes engagement and participation, which can enhance student learning outcomes and promote skill development (3.20) are sometimes manifested, while, Professional development opportunities focused on innovative teaching methods and active learning can help TLE teachers develop skills related to lesson planning, instructional design, and student engagement, which can enhance student learning outcomes (2.45) and Innovative teaching methods that incorporate active learning strategies, such as project-based learning and problem-solving, can help TLE students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts and develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills (2.40) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.95 denotes extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of active learning is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Active learning is defined as any instructional method that engages students in the learning process through activities such as problem-solving, discussions, and collaborative projects, rather than passive listening or note-taking (Prince, Felder, Brent, 2007). This approach encourages students to take responsibility for their own learning, develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and apply knowledge in real-world contexts (Bonwell Eison, 1991). In TLE, active learning can take various forms such as hands-on training, simulations, role-playing, and project-based learning, among others. Several studies have shown the benefits of active learning in TLE. For instance, a study by Zhang, Wei, and Wang (2019) found that project-based learning, a form of active learning, can improve students' problem-solving ability and creativity in TLE. Another study by Kamaruddin, Yusoff, and Bakar (2020) reported that hands-on training, another form of active learning, can enhance students' practical

skills and confidence in TLE. Furthermore, a meta-analysis conducted by Freeman et al. (2014) found that students in active learning classrooms had higher exam scores and lower failure rates compared to those in traditional lecture-based classrooms. The importance of active learning in TLE goes beyond improving students' academic performance. Active learning can also contribute to the development of a skilled workforce that can meet the demands of the industry. As TLE aims to provide students with practical skills and competencies, active learning methods that simulate real-world situations and challenges can better prepare students for their future careers (Kezar Gehrke, 2015). Additionally, active learning can foster creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurship, which are essential qualities for success in the rapidly changing technological landscape (Lindgren McDaniel, 2018). In addition, active learning in TLE helps students to develop lifelong learning skills that are necessary for their pro-

Table 9. Extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of active learning

No	Active Learning	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Active learning is a student-centered approach to teaching that prioritizes engagement and participation, which can enhance student learning outcomes and promote skill development.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
2	Innovative teaching methods that incorporate active learning strategies, such as project-based learning and problem-solving, can help TLE students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts and develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	2.40	Less Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on innovative teaching methods and active learning can help TLE teachers develop skills related to lesson planning, instructional design, and student engagement, which can enhance student learning outcomes.	2.45	Less Extensive
4	TLE teachers who incorporate active learning strategies into their instruction are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of their students and promote inclusive and equitable classrooms.	3.45	Extensive
5	A focus on active learning as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to prepare students for success in the rapidly-evolving technological landscape by promoting skills such as creativity, adaptability, and collaboration, which are essential for success in the workforce.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.95	Moderately Extensive

professional growth and development. As noted by Sarmiento and Atanante (2020), active learning fosters a self-directed learning approach that encourages students to take responsibility for their learning and seek opportunities for continuous learning and improvement. This is particularly important in TLE, where technological advancements and changes in the workplace require workers to update their skills and knowledge regularly.

Table 10 shows the extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of integration of technology. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: TLE teachers who incorporate technology into their instruction are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of their students, particularly those who may be more comfortable with digital technologies than traditional classroom methods (4.40) is always man-

The integration of technology in innovative teaching methods is becoming increasingly important in technology and livelihood education (TLE). Technology offers various tools and resources that can enhance teaching and learning, as well as promote creativity and critical thinking among students. According to Lim and Zhang (2019), the use of technology in education has shifted from a focus on technology as a separate subject to technology as an integrated tool for teaching and learning. This shift requires teachers to develop their knowledge and skills in using technology to enhance their teaching practices. In a study by Hsu, Wang, and Huang (2020), it was found that the integration of technology in teaching can increase students' engagement, motivation, and interest in learning. The study also revealed that teachers who effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices are more likely to be successful in achieving their learning objectives. This highlights the importance of professional

ifested, The integration of technology in TLE instruction is essential to prepare students for success in the 21st-century workforce, where technology skills are increasingly in demand (3.50) and Professional development opportunities focused on technology integration can help TLE teachers develop skills related to instructional design, software and hardware selection, and digital assessment, which can enhance student learning outcomes (3.35) are oftentimes manifested, while; A focus on technology integration as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote access and equity in education by ensuring that all students have access to the digital tools and resources they need to succeed (3.34) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.57 denotes extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of integration of technology is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

development for TLE teachers to enhance their technology integration skills. The integration of technology as a component of innovative teaching methods in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is important in providing students with relevant and up-to-date knowledge and skills. According to Guzman and Dela Cruz (2019), the integration of technology in TLE subjects enables teachers to design and implement effective learning experiences that promote student engagement, interaction, and collaboration. Technology integration can also provide students with opportunities to develop essential 21st-century skills such as digital literacy, critical thinking, and problem-solving. Furthermore, a study conducted by Madelo (2020) emphasized the importance of using technology-based teaching strategies in TLE subjects to promote active learning and enhance student engagement. The study recommended that teachers should undergo training and professional development programs that focus on technology

Table 10. Extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of integration of technology

No	Integration of Technology	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The integration of technology in TLE instruction is essential to prepare students for success in the 21st-century workforce, where technology skills are increasingly in demand.	3.50	Extensive
2	Innovative teaching methods that incorporate technology, such as online learning platforms and digital simulations, can enhance student engagement and promote active learning.	3.40	Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on technology integration can help TLE teachers develop skills related to instructional design, software and hardware selection, and digital assessment, which can enhance student learning outcomes.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
4	TLE teachers who incorporate technology into their instruction are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of their students, particularly those who may be more comfortable with digital technologies than traditional classroom methods.	4.40	Very Extensive
5	A focus on technology integration as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote access and equity in education by ensuring that all students have access to the digital tools and resources they need to succeed.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.57	Extensive

integration and the use of innovative teaching methods.

Table 11 shows the extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of real-world connections. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Professional development opportunities focused on real-world connections can help TLE teachers develop skills related to curriculum design, industry partnerships, and career exploration, which can enhance student learning outcomes and promote workforce readiness (4.50) and A focus on real-world connections as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote equity and access in education by providing all students with opportunities to explore and pursue career-related interests, regardless of their background or experience level (4.20) are always manifested; while, TLE teachers who incorpo-

rate real-world connections into their instruction are better equipped to meet the needs of students who are seeking to gain practical experience and develop career-related skills (3.15), Innovative teaching methods that incorporate real-world connections, such as project-based learning and internships, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with opportunities to work on real-world challenges and tasks (3.10) and Real-world connections are a key component of innovative teaching methods in TLE because they help students understand how the skills and knowledge they are learning in the classroom can be applied in real-world contexts (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.59 denotes extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of changes in behavior is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Innovative teaching methods that incorporate real-world connections have become increasingly important in technology and livelihood education (TLE) as they help students to apply their knowledge and skills to practical and relevant situations. Real-world connections help to make learning more meaningful and relevant for students. When students can see how the concepts and skills they are learning apply to real-world situations, they are more likely to be engaged and motivated to learn. Real-world connections can also help students to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills as they apply their knowledge and skills to practical situations. Incorporating real-world connections into TLE can also help to prepare students for future careers. By providing opportunities to apply their knowledge and skills to real-world situations, students can develop the necessary competencies and confidence to succeed in the workforce. Real-world connections can also help students to understand the relevance of

their education and how it can be applied in different contexts. A study by Srisa Ard and Kanta Jantasee (2018) in Thailand explored the effectiveness of an innovative teaching method that incorporated real-world connections in TLE. The study found that students who participated in the program had higher levels of motivation and interest in learning, and were better able to apply their knowledge and skills to real-world situations. Similarly, a study by Zulfiqar Ali and colleagues (2019) in Pakistan examined the impact of a project-based learning approach that incorporated real-world connections in TLE. The study found that students who participated in the program had higher levels of engagement, motivation, and critical thinking skills. Another study by Oh and Yoo (2021) in South Korea explored the impact of a STEM-based TLE program that incorporated real-world connections. The study found that students who participated in the program had higher levels of interest and motivation in learning, and were better able to

Table 11. Extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of real-world connections

No	Real-world Connections	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Real-world connections are a key component of innovative teaching methods in TLE because they help students understand how the skills and knowledge they are learning in the classroom can be applied in real-world contexts.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
2	Innovative teaching methods that incorporate real-world connections, such as project-based learning and internships, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with opportunities to work on real-world challenges and tasks.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on real-world connections can help TLE teachers develop skills related to curriculum design, industry partnerships, and career exploration, which can enhance student learning outcomes and promote workforce readiness.	4.50	Very Extensive
4	TLE teachers who incorporate real-world connections into their instruction are better equipped to meet the needs of students who are seeking to gain practical experience and develop career-related skills.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on real-world connections as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote equity and access in education by providing all students with opportunities to explore and pursue career-related interests, regardless of their background or experience level.	4.20	Very Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.59	Extensive

apply their knowledge and skills to real-world situations.

Table 12 shows the extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of differentiated instructions. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Innovative teaching methods that incorporate differentiated instruction, such as flexible grouping and personalized learning, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with individualized support and tailored instruction (4.10), and Differentiated instruction is an essential component of innovative teaching methods in TLE because it helps teachers meet the diverse needs of their students and promote inclusivity in the classroom (3.40) are

Differentiated instruction is a teaching approach that tailors instruction to meet the unique learning needs, abilities, and interests of individual learners. In the context of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), the use of differentiated instruction can be crucial in engaging and motivating students to learn and pursue their interests and passions in various fields such as technology, entrepreneurship, and vocational skills. One study by Lin and Tsai (2018) highlights the importance of using differentiated instruction to improve students' learning outcomes and engagement in TLE. The researchers found that by using differentiated instruction, teachers were able to better understand students' individual needs and interests, which resulted in increased student motivation and better learning outcomes. Brown and Cooper (2019) emphasized the importance of using differentiated instruction in vocational education to meet the diverse learning needs of students. The researchers found that differentiated instruction helped students improve their self-esteem, academic performance, and career readiness. Differentiated instruction is an innovative teaching

oftentimes manifested while, A focus on differentiated instruction as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote equity and access in education by ensuring that all students have access to high-quality instruction that meets their individual needs and supports their academic and career goals (3.20) and TLE teachers who incorporate differentiated instruction into their instruction are better equipped to meet the needs of students with varying levels of background knowledge, learning styles, and abilities (3.15) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.39 denotes extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of differentiated instructions is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

approach that recognizes and accommodates the individual needs and interests of students. It emphasizes the use of various teaching strategies, techniques, and materials to support learning and ensure that all students are challenged and engaged in the classroom. In the Philippine setting, differentiated instruction has been recognized as an effective teaching strategy that promotes inclusivity and diversity in the classroom. One study conducted by Cagas, et al. (2019) explored the effectiveness of differentiated instruction in enhancing the academic performance of Grade 7 students in a technology and livelihood education (TLE) class. The study found that the implementation of differentiated instruction significantly improved the academic performance of the students. The researchers noted that the use of varied instructional materials and strategies enabled the students to explore and discover their interests and potentials. Moreover, Dela Cruz (2019) highlighted the significance of differentiated instruction in promoting inclusivity and equity in the TLE classroom. The author stressed that differentiated instruction is a vital tool in addressing

Table 12. Extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of differentiated instructions

No	Differentiated Instructions	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Differentiated instruction is an essential component of innovative teaching methods in TLE because it helps teachers meet the diverse needs of their students and promote inclusivity in the classroom.	3.40	Extensive
2	Innovative teaching methods that incorporate differentiated instruction, such as flexible grouping and personalized learning, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with individualized support and tailored instruction.	4.10	Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on differentiated instruction can help TLE teachers develop skills related to assessing student needs, adapting instruction to meet individual student needs, and designing flexible learning environments.	2.50	Moderately Extensive
4	TLE teachers who incorporate differentiated instruction into their instruction are better equipped to meet the needs of students with varying levels of background knowledge, learning styles, and abilities.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on differentiated instruction as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote equity and access in education by ensuring that all students have access to high-quality instruction that meets their individual needs and supports their academic and career goals.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
	Overall Mean	3.39	Moderately Extensive

the diverse needs of students, including those with special needs, and ensuring that all students have equal opportunities to learn and succeed.

Table 13 shows the extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of collaborative learning. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: TLE teachers who incorporate collaborative learning into their instruction are better equipped to meet the needs of students who thrive in group settings and value peer interaction and feedback (3.15), and Innovative teaching methods that incorporate collaborative learning, such as project-based learning and team-based assignments, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with opportunities to work with others and learn from their peers (3.10) are sometimes manifested, while, Collaborative learning is an essential component of innova-

tive teaching methods in TLE because it helps students develop teamwork and communication skills, which are highly valued in the workplace (2.40), Professional development opportunities focused on collaborative learning can help TLE teachers develop skills related to designing effective group work activities, facilitating classroom discussions, and promoting active participation (2.30) and A focus on collaborative learning as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote inclusivity and diversity in the classroom by providing all students with opportunities to learn from and collaborate with peers from different backgrounds and experiences (2.20) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.63 denotes extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of collaborative learning is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Collaborative learning is an approach in which students work together in groups to achieve shared learning goals. In technology and livelihood education, collaborative learning can be an effective tool to help students develop problem-solving, teamwork, and communication skills. It also encourages students to engage with the subject matter and take ownership of their learning. Abdulrahman et al. (2019) found that collaborative learning can enhance students' academic performance, as well as their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Similarly, a study by Liu et al. (2018) demonstrated that collaborative learning can improve students' learning outcomes, particularly in the areas of teamwork, communication, and creativity. Sun et al. (2020) focused specifically on collaborative learning in the context of engineering education. The authors found that collaborative learning can help students develop both technical and non-technical skills, such as project management and communica-

tion. The study also highlighted the importance of the instructor's role in promoting effective collaboration, through strategies such as clear communication and providing feedback. Another advantage of collaborative learning is that it can increase student motivation and engagement. According to a study by Estigoy and Agravante (2018), students who participate in collaborative learning are more likely to be motivated and engaged in their studies than those who work alone. This is because collaborative learning provides students with a sense of ownership over their learning and allows them to take an active role in the learning process. Finally, collaborative learning can help to develop students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. According to a study by Rodriguez and Diaz (2019), collaborative learning can help students to develop these skills by exposing them to different perspectives and encouraging them to analyze and evaluate information. This can help students to become more independent thinkers

Table 13. Extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of collaboration and partnerships

No	Collaboration and Partnerships	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Collaborative learning is an essential component of innovative teaching methods in TLE because it helps students develop teamwork and communication skills, which are highly valued in the work-place.	2.40	Less Extensive
2	Innovative teaching methods that incorporate collaborative learning, such as project-based learning and team-based assignments, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with opportunities to work with others and learn from their peers.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on collaborative learning can help TLE teachers develop skills related to designing effective group work activities, facilitating classroom discussions, and promoting active participation.	2.30	Less Extensive
4	TLE teachers who incorporate collaborative learning into their instruction are better equipped to meet the needs of students who thrive in group settings and value peer interaction and feedback.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on collaborative learning as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote inclusivity and diversity in the classroom by providing all students with opportunities to learn from and collaborate with peers from different backgrounds and experiences.	2.20	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.63	Moderately Extensive

and better equipped to handle real-world challenges in the workplace.

Table 14 shows the extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of reflection and feedback. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Reflection and feedback are essential components of innovative teaching methods in TLE because they help students develop critical thinking and self-assessment skills, which are highly valued in the workplace (3.40), Innovative teaching methods that incorporate reflection and feedback, such as self-assessment tools and peer review, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with opportunities to reflect on their learning and receive constructive feedback from others (3.30) and TLE teachers who incorporate reflection and feedback into their instruction are better equipped to meet

Reflection and feedback are crucial components of innovative teaching methods as they support student learning outcomes and improve teacher effectiveness. According to Manrique, Jiménez, and Padilla (2019), reflective teaching enhances teachers' self-efficacy, which positively influences student learning outcomes. Reflective teaching allows teachers to examine and evaluate their teaching strategies, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and develop action plans to improve their instructional practices. Feedback, on the other hand, helps students understand their strengths and weaknesses and provides guidance on how to improve their learning outcomes. According to Hattie and Timperley (2018), feedback is one of the most powerful tools for enhancing student learning outcomes. Effective feedback provides students with clear learning targets, identifies their current level of performance, and offers guidance on how to close the gap between their current and desired performance. Reflection and feedback are

the needs of students who value self-directed learning and desire feedback to improve their skills and knowledge (3.15) are oftentimes manifested, while, Professional development opportunities focused on reflection and feedback can help TLE teachers develop skills related to designing effective feedback mechanisms, using data to inform instruction, and promoting a growth mindset among students (2.30) and A focus on reflection and feedback as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote continuous improvement in teaching and learning by encouraging teachers and students to reflect on their practices and make adjustments based on feedback and evidence (2.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.87 denotes extent of the use of innovative teaching methods in terms of reflection and feedback is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

also essential components of innovative teaching methods as they support the development of critical thinking skills. Reflection allows teachers to critically analyze their teaching practices and identify areas that need improvement, while feedback helps students develop critical thinking skills by providing them with information on how to improve their learning outcomes (Manrique et al., 2019). In addition, reflection and feedback facilitate the development of metacognitive skills, which are essential for successful learning outcomes. Metacognition involves thinking about one's thinking, which enables students to develop self-awareness and self-regulation skills that enhance their learning outcomes. Pacoma and Bautista (2021), feedback was found to be effective in improving the performance of students in TLE. The study revealed that students who received regular feedback on their performance demonstrated significant improvements in their learning outcomes. Lastly, the study by Canayon (2020)

Table 14. Extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of reflection and feedback

No	Reflection and Feedback	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Reflection and feedback are essential components of innovative teaching methods in TLE because they help students develop critical thinking and self-assessment skills, which are highly valued in the workplace.	3.40	Extensive
2	Innovative teaching methods that incorporate reflection and feedback, such as self-assessment tools and peer review, can enhance student engagement and promote skill development by providing students with opportunities to reflect on their learning and receive constructive feedback from others.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
3	Professional development opportunities focused on reflection and feedback can help TLE teachers develop skills related to designing effective feedback mechanisms, using data to inform instruction, and promoting a growth mindset among students.	2.30	Less Extensive
4	TLE teachers who incorporate reflection and feedback into their instruction are better equipped to meet the needs of students who value self-directed learning and desire feedback to improve their skills and knowledge.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
5	A focus on reflection and feedback as part of innovative teaching methods in TLE can help to promote continuous improvement in teaching and learning by encouraging teachers and students to reflect on their practices and make adjustments based on feedback and evidence.	2.20	Less Extensive
	Overall Mean	2.87	Moderately Extensive

emphasized the importance of using reflective feedback as a means of promoting teacher professional development in TLE. The study revealed that reflective feedback not only helped TLE teachers improve their teaching practices but also contributed to their personal and professional growth.

Table 15 shows the summary of the extent of use of innovative teaching methods. The

result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: real-world connections (3.59) and integration of technology (3.57) are oftentimes manifested, while, active learning (2.95), reflection and feedback (2.87) and collaborative learning (2.63) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.16 denotes is moderately manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 15. Summary of the Extent of the Use of Innovative Teaching Methods

No	Innovative Teaching Method	Mean
1	Active Learning	2.95
2	Integration of Technology	3.57
3	Real-world Connections	3.59
4	Differentiated Instructions	3.39
5	Collaborative Learning	2.63
6	Reflection and Feedback	2.87
	Overall Mean	3.16

Active learning is a student-centered approach that encourages learners to participate actively in the learning process. It involves hands-on activities, discussions, problem-solving, and critical thinking exercises. Innovative teaching methods, such as flipped classrooms, inquiry-based learning, and project-based learning, promote active learning by shifting the focus from passive listening to active participation. Students are more engaged, motivated, and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter through these methods. Technology plays a crucial role in modern education. Innovative teaching methods leverage technology to enhance the learning experience. This includes using multimedia resources, educational apps, online platforms, and interactive tools. Technology enables teachers to present information in diverse formats, cater to different learning styles, and provide immediate feedback to students. It also facilitates personalized learning, as students can access resources at their own pace and explore topics that interest them. Vir-

tual reality, augmented reality, simulations, and gamified learning are some examples of how technology is integrated into teaching to make it more engaging and interactive. Innovative teaching methods aim to bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and real-world applications. By making connections to real-life situations, students can better understand the relevance and practicality of what they are learning. Teachers employ various strategies such as case studies, problem-solving tasks, and field trips to connect academic content to real-world contexts. This approach enhances students' critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and prepares them for future challenges they may encounter in their careers. Students have diverse learning needs, abilities, and interests. Differentiated instruction is an innovative teaching approach that acknowledges these differences and provides customized learning experiences to meet individual students' needs. By tailoring instruction based on students' strengths, weaknesses, and preferences, teachers can maximize

learning outcomes. Differentiated instruction includes flexible grouping, varied instructional materials, and individualized assignments. It fosters a supportive learning environment where every student can succeed and reach their full potential. Collaborative learning emphasizes the importance of cooperative work and peer interaction. Students learn from and with each other, fostering social and communication skills. Innovative teaching methods incorporate collaborative learning through group projects, discussions, debates, and problem-solving tasks. Collaborative learning enhances critical thinking, teamwork, and communication skills. It also exposes students to diverse perspectives and promotes a sense of community and shared responsibility for learning.

Significant Relationship TLE Teachers’ Professional Development and The Use of Innovative Teaching Methods

It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between TLE teachers’ professional development ($r=0.870$; $p_i.001$) and use of innovative teaching methods. Table 16 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between TLE teachers’ professional development and the use of innovative teaching methods. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between TLE teachers’ professional development and the use of innovative teaching methods must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 16. Significant Relationship between TLE Teachers’ Professional Development and the Use of Innovative Teaching Methods

Variables	TLE Teachers’ Professional Development	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Use of Innovative Teaching Methods	0.870	<0.001	Significant	Reject H0

*significant @ $p<0.05$.

Professional development programs serve as a crucial platform for TLE teachers to acquire up-to-date knowledge and skills relevant to their field. Such programs enable teachers to stay informed about the latest advancements, pedagogical approaches, and teaching methodologies. By expanding their knowledge base, teachers gain a deeper understanding of how to effectively incorporate innovative teaching methods into their lessons. Through professional development, TLE teachers are introduced to a wide range of innovative teaching methods. These methods encompass dynamic approaches such as project-based learning, inquiry-based learn-

ing, technology integration, and experiential learning. As teachers engage in professional development activities, they gain insights into the rationale, strategies, and practical implementation of these methods. This knowledge empowers TLE teachers to adapt and apply innovative teaching techniques to suit the needs of their students, creating engaging and impactful learning experiences. Professional development equips TLE teachers with the necessary tools to foster active and student-centered learning environments. Innovative teaching methods often prioritize student engagement, collaboration, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. With the

acquired knowledge and skills, TLE teachers can design lessons that encourage students to become active participants in their own learning journey. By integrating hands-on activities, real-world applications, and authentic assessments, teachers can stimulate students' curiosity, motivation, and creativity. The use of innovative teaching methods, facilitated by professional development, leads to improved student outcomes. By employing approaches that align with students' diverse learning styles, interests, and abilities, TLE teachers create inclusive classrooms that cater to individual needs. Innovative methods promote higher-order thinking, communication skills, and teamwork, enabling students to acquire not only subject-specific knowledge but also transferable skills essential for future career success. As a result, students' academic performance, self-confidence, and overall engagement in the learning process are enhanced.

The Domains TLE Teachers' Professional Development Significantly Influence Use of Innovative Teaching Methods

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) plays a crucial role in equipping students with practical skills and knowledge necessary for various trades and livelihoods. The professional development of TLE teachers is essential to enhance their instructional practices and effectively prepare students for the demands of the modern world. By incorporating innovative teaching methods supported by technology, TLE teachers can have a profound influence on students' learning outcomes. This essay will discuss and explain the significant influence of technology and livelihood education teacher's professional development with the use of innovative teaching methods, supported by relevant scholarly research. Technology allows TLE teachers to access the latest information and advancements in various fields. According to Bawane and Spector (2013), the use of technol-

Table 17 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the TLE teachers' professional development that significantly influence use of innovative teaching methods. Domains of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of delivering content knowledge (0.001), pedagogical knowledge(0.010), assessment and evaluation (0.00) technology integration (0.000), and leadership and advocacy (0.012) significantly influence use of innovative teaching methods; while industrial partnership (0.052) and cultural competence (0.051) are not significantly influential in the use of innovative teaching methods. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.873 suggests that the domains of TLE teachers' professional development 87.3In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (238.897) and F-statistic is significant $p_i.001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of the use of innovative teaching methods.

ogy in professional development helps teachers to keep up with the rapidly changing knowledge and skills required for effective instruction. Online resources, professional development platforms, and networking opportunities provide teachers with relevant and accurate information about current industry practices, emerging technologies, and changing market demands. Innovative teaching methods supported by technology enable TLE teachers to employ a wide range of instructional strategies. Borko, Whitcomb, and Liston (2009) emphasize that innovative teaching practices provide opportunities for active participation, critical thinking, problem-solving, and practical skill development. Multimedia presentations, interactive simulations, virtual reality, and augmented reality create engaging and immersive learning experiences for students. These methods foster deeper under-

Table 17. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of TLE Teachers' Professional Development That Significantly Influence Use Of Innovative Teaching Methods

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decision	
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	
H	(Intercept)	0.213	0.175	1.076	0.280	
	CK	0.807	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315
0.001	*Reject H0					
	PK	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196
0.010	*Reject H0					
	AE	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038
0.000	*Reject H0					
	TI	0.683	0.086	0.499	5.654	0.001
0.000	*Reject H0					
	IP	0.441	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196
0.052	Accept H0					
	CC	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038
0.051	Accept H0					
	LA	0.441	0.108	0.499	2.098	0.038
0.012	*Reject H0					
<hr/>						
R²	= 0.873					
F-value	= 238.897					
p-value	<0.001					
*Significant @ p<0.05						

standing and application of concepts. Technology facilitates collaboration and networking among TLE teachers, leading to the sharing of ideas, resources, and best practices. Wang, Chen, and Chen (2017) note that online platforms, forums, and social media groups provide spaces for teachers to connect, exchange experiences, and seek advice. Collaboration fosters professional growth, encourages the adoption of innovative teaching methods, and promotes a culture of continuous improvement among teachers. Technology empowers TLE teachers

to provide personalized and differentiated instruction. Through learning management systems, educational apps, and online assessment tools, teachers can track student progress, identify areas for improvement, and tailor instruction accordingly. According to Hattie (2012), personalized instruction has a significant positive effect on student learning outcomes. By leveraging technology, teachers can meet the diverse needs of students and provide targeted interventions and support.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The TLE teachers' professional development in terms of leadership and advocacy (3.67), assessment and evaluation (3.61), pedagogical knowledge (3.56), and content knowledge (3.54) are oftentimes manifested; while, industry partnership (2.80) and technology integration (2.61) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.25 denotes extent of TLE teachers' professional development is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

The extent of use of innovative teaching methods in terms of real-world connections (3.59) and integration of technology (3.57) are oftentimes manifested, while, active learning (2.95), reflection and feedback (2.87) and collaborative learning (2.63) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.16 denotes is moderately manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between TLE teachers' professional development ($r=0.870$; $p<.001$)

and use of innovative teaching methods. Domains of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of delivering content knowledge (0.001), pedagogical knowledge (0.010), assessment and evaluation (0.00) technology integration (0.000), and leadership and advocacy (0.012) significantly influence use of innovative teaching methods; while industrial partnership (0.052) and cultural competence (0.051) are not significantly influential in the use of innovative teaching methods.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The TLE teachers' professional development in terms of leadership and advocacy, assessment and evaluation, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge, industry partnership technology denotes extent of TLE teachers' professional development is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The use of innovative teaching methods in terms of real-world connections, integration of technology, active learning, reflection and feedback collaborative learning denotes is moderately mani-

fested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between TLE teachers' professional development and use of innovative teaching methods. Domains of TLE teachers' professional development in terms of delivering content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, assessment and evaluation technology integration, and leadership and advocacy significantly influenced the use of innovative teaching methods.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor: May provide adequate resources and support through allocating sufficient resources, including funding, technology infrastructure, and professional development opportunities, to support the industry partnership and cultural competence. This will enable teachers to effectively implement new strategies and stay updated with the latest advancements in their respective fields. Encourage collaboration among teachers within the district by organizing workshops, seminars, and networking events. Facilitate the sharing of best practices, lesson plans, and resources to promote a culture of continuous improvement. This collaborative environment will enhance the professional development of teachers and ultimately improve the quality of instruction in technology and livelihood education. This develops cultural competence and industrial partnership. School Principal. May foster a supportive and inclusive environment where teachers feel encouraged to experiment with innovative teaching methods. Recognize and reward teachers who demonstrate excellence in integrating technology and implementing innovative instructional practices. This will motivate teachers to further enhance their professional development and improve student outcomes. Arrange regu-

lar professional development sessions focusing on innovative teaching methods and the integration of technology. Collaborate with external experts, industry professionals, and educational organizations to offer workshops, seminars, and training programs for teachers. These opportunities will equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively incorporate technology into their teaching practices. The Teachers. May engage in continuous professional development an take active role in professional development opportunities offered by the school district, educational institutions, and online platforms. Stay updated with the latest research, trends, and advancements in technology and livelihood education. Engage in self-reflection and seek feedback from peers and mentors to continuously improve instructional practices. Embrace a growth mindset and be open to adopting innovative teaching methods. Be willing to explore new technologies, experiment with different instructional strategies, and collaborate with colleagues. Emphasize the importance of lifelong learning and continuously strive to enhance professional skills and knowledge. The Future Researchers. May investigate the impact of innovative teaching methods through conduct research to explore the impact of innovative teaching methods supported by technology on student learning outcomes in technology and livelihood education. Identify barriers and challenges faced by teachers in industry partnership and cultural competence. Investigate factors such as access to technology, teacher readiness, support systems, and institutional policies. This research will help develop strategies to overcome these challenges and promote successful implementation of innovative teaching methods.

5. References

Abdullah, F., Ahmed, M. (2018). The impact of gamification on learning and instruction in TLE. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 13(5), 152-164. doi: 10.3991/ijet.v13i05.8589

Abdulrahman, N. M., Abbas, N. M., Aljuaid, S. M., Alshehri, S. M. (2019). Effectiveness of collaborative learning in enhancing students' academic performance and critical thinking. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(12), 2664-2670. doi: 10.13189/ujer.2019.071208

Adajar, M. M., Pinpin, M. S., Salvador, M. P. (2021). Real-life application of technology and livelihood education (TLE) in Senior High School. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 30(5), 3765-3774.

Akarsu, B., Iyibilgin, B. (2020). Examining the Relationship between Content Knowledge and Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Vocational Education. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 12(1), 208-220.

Alao, A. A., Shamsudeen, A. A. (2022). Teachers' cultural competence and diversity management: Implications for students' academic and social success. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 12(1), 1-11.

Alinsunod, J. M. G., Caballero, R. J. M., Abao, J. M. V. (2021). Professional Development Needs of TLE Teachers in a Philippine Public Secondary School. *Journal of Technical Education*, 2(2), 33-44.

Alvarez, J. G., Cuaresma, R. (2019). Assessment practices and feedback mechanisms of technology and livelihood education teachers in a Philippine university. *Journal of Technical Education*, 70(2), 86-102.

Arellano, R. M., Cadiz, E. S., Madolid, J. J. (2020). The assessment and evaluation practices of technology and livelihood education (TLE) teachers. *International Journal of Scientific Technology Research*, 9(3), 717-722.

Bawane, J., Spector, J. M. (2019). Emerging technologies for education: A retrospective. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 67(5), 1047-1064. doi: 10.1007/s11423-019-09702-8

Baser, B., Gunay, M. (2021). The Effect of Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Vocational High School Teachers on Vocational Students' Academic Achievement. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 7(1), 1-14.

Bautista, R. J. S., Talaguit, A. M. (2021). Technology and Livelihood Education in the Philippines: Challenges and Prospects. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 17(3), 111-122.

Bonwell, C. C., Eison, J. A. (1991). *Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom*. Washington, DC: School of Education and Human Development, George Washington University.

Brown, J., Cooper, R. (2019). Meeting the diverse needs of students in vocational education: the importance of differentiated instruction. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 71(2), 161-178.

Cagas, J. G., Aballe, J. A., Laguador, J. M. (2019). Effectiveness of differentiated instruction in enhancing academic performance in Technology and Livelihood Education. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 9(1), 433-438.

Canayon, R. A. (2020). Using reflective feedback to promote teacher professional development

in technology and livelihood education. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 16(2), 33-41.

Canencia, J., Jusay, M., Acedillo, A., Pongos, J. (2021). Industry partnership: A key to enhancing the TLE assessment tool development. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 17(2), 143-155.

Castillo, A. M., Gomez, M. L. R., Icotanim, J. (2020). Challenges and coping mechanisms of technology integration of TLE teachers in Region I. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology*, 11(4), 168-173.

Chai, C. S., Koh, J. H. L., Tsai, C.-C. (2018). Examining TPACK among K-12 online distance educators in the Asia-Pacific region. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 34(5), 20-33. doi: 10.14742/ajet.3531

Chen, C. H., Wu, P. H. (2021). The effect of teacher professional development on Technology and Livelihood Education. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 31(3), 745-761.

Chen, W., Wu, H. K., Wu, Y. T., Liu, T. C. (2019). Developing and evaluating a web-based professional development program to enhance TLE teachers' cultural competence. *Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 28(6), 503-512. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-019-00486-8>

Dede, C. (2017). Immersive interfaces for engagement and learning. *Science*, 357(6359), 1339-1340. doi: 10.1126/science.aao4585

De Boer, G. E., van den Berg, E. (2019). Promoting relevance and authenticity in vocational education: A review of evidence. *Journal of Vocational Education Training*, 71(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2018.1541602>

De Los Reyes, J. A., Estavillo, L. A., Gicana, R. G. (2019). Project-based learning in technology and livelihood education: Students' learning experiences and outcomes. *Journal of Industrial Teacher Education*, 56(1), 97-122.

De Guzman, R. G., Navarro, E. S. (2020). Integration of industry-oriented projects in enhancing TLE instruction. *International Journal of Social Science and Business*, 4(1), 60-70.

Dela Cruz, J. B. (2019). Differentiated Instruction: A strategy for inclusive teaching in Technology and Livelihood Education. *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Social Sciences*, 1(2), 23-27.

De Los Reyes, J. A., Estavillo, L. A., Gicana, R. G. (2019). Project-based learning in technology and livelihood education: Students' learning experiences and outcomes. *Journal of Industrial Teacher Education*, 56(1), 97-122.

Delos Santos, J. A. N., Acedera, K. A. (2018). Professional Development Programs for Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in the Philippines: Impact on Teaching Practices and Student Learning Outcomes. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 6(2), 71-79.

Díaz-Maggioli, G. (2018). *Teaching with intention: Defining beliefs, aligning practice, taking action*, K-5. Stenhouse Publishers.

Dizon, E. M., Ricafort, E. D. (2018). Differentiated Instruction in Technology and Livelihood Education: Towards a Framework for Instructional Planning. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(32), 91-100.

Döş, İ., Döş, Y. (2020). The Impact of Professional Development Programs on Technology Integration in Technology and Livelihood Education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(3), 7-17.

Duhaney, D. C., Feir, E. (2020). Teacher leadership and empowerment: Building capacity for educational reform. *Journal of Educational Change*, 21(2), 179-196.

El Rafei, M., Abou-Elhamd, M. (2019). The Impact of Teachers' Content Knowledge on Students' Learning Outcomes in Technology Education. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 31(4), 589-605.

Estigoy, L. B., Agravante, M. A. (2018). The Effects of Collaborative Learning on Student Engagement in a Technology and Livelihood Education Class. *Journal of Research in Technical Education*, 3(1), 26-33.

Ertmer, P. A., Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T., Sadik, O., Sendurur, E., Sendurur, P. (2012). Teacher beliefs and technology integration practices: A critical relationship. *Computers Education*, 59(2), 423-435. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2012.02.001

Fadul, M. A. L., Sarmiento, A. D., Soriano, E. M. (2020). Use of technology in assessment and evaluation: A basis for upgrading teaching and learning strategies in technology and livelihood education. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 12(1), 56-66.

Fernandez, M. A. G., Galedo, P. L. B., Rosales, M. L. T. (2021). Technology integration in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) program of secondary schools. *International Journal of Academic Research and Development*, 6(1), 1-8.

Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23), 8410-8415.

Gamboa, E. A., Encarnacion, E. M. (2019). An exploration of the factors that influence TLE teacher performance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(4), 55-64.

Garingan, J. A. T., Arreola, R. B. (2020). Competencies of Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in the 21st Century. *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 10(4), 667-687.

Gikandi, J. W., Morrow, D., Davis, N. E. (2011). Online formative assessment in higher education: A review of the literature. *Computers Education*, 57(4), 2333-2351. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2011.06.004

Guzman, J. F., Dela Cruz, D. A. (2019). The impact of technology integration in the teaching and learning of technology and livelihood education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(32), 19-24.

Halverson, E. R., Sheridan, K. (2018). The maker movement in education. *Harvard Educational Review*, 88(1), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.17763/0017-8055.88.1.1>

Hargreaves, A., O'Connor, M. T. (2018). Collaborative professionalism as educational change: A framework for building capacity. *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*, 3(2), 88-104.

Harlen, W. (2012). Assessment for learning: A brief overview of theory and research. Assessment Reform Group. Retrieved from <https://www.cambridgeassessment.org.uk/Images/152649-assessment-for-learning-a-brief-overview-of-theory-and-research.pdf>

Hattie, J., Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of educational research*, 77(1), 81-112. doi: 10.3102/003465430298487.

He, Y., Lei, J. (2019). Examining the Impact of Professional Development on Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Practice. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 70(1), 77-92.

Hernandez, J. C., Saenz, R. (2019). Culturally responsive teaching and cultural competence in teacher education. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 21(1), 41-53.

Hsu, C. H., Wang, C. Y., Huang, T. C. (2020). The effects of technology integration on students' learning performance in higher education: A meta-analysis. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 20(5), 55-77. doi: 10.12738/estp.2020.5.287

Ismael, M. A. B., Maguad, B. S. (2021). Enhancing Technology and Livelihood Education Teacher Education Program in the Philippines. *Journal of Technology and Education*, 13(1), 19-34.

Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R. T., Smith, K. A. (2018). Cooperative learning: Improving university instruction by basing practice on validated theory. *Journal on Excellence in College Teaching*, 29(4), 81-103.

Jones, S., Robinson, M. (2019). Content Knowledge for Vocational Education and Training Teachers in Australia: An Investigation of Teachers' Perceptions. *International Journal of Training Research*, 17(1), 1-16.

Kamaruddin, S. A., Yusoff, A. R. M., Bakar, A. A. A. (2020). The impact of hands-on training in enhancing practical skills and self-confidence among technical education students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(8), 122-138.

Kaur, R., Javed, U. (2020). Challenges and opportunities of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the 21st century. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 17(1), 1-18.

Kim, S. H., Lee, S. (2019). Technology Integration in Technology and Livelihood Education: The Role of TPACK in Student Learning Outcomes. *Sustainability*, 11(6), 1537.

Khoo, E., Gao, X. (2019). Real-world learning and technology integration in secondary STEM education: A systematic review. *Computers Education*, 142, 103649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103649>

Koh, J. H. L., Divaharan, S. (2018). TPACK in action: A study of teacher professional development in technology integration. *Journal of Educational Technology Society*, 21(2), 222-237.

Koh, J. H. L., Chai, C. S., Tsai, C. C. (2019). Demystifying TPACK and its impact on teachers' readiness to engage in digital pedagogies. *Educational Technology Research and Development*

Largo, J. D., Delos Reyes, F. R., San Jose, J. D. (2019). Industry linkage of the senior high school TLE program of a private university. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 15(2), 89-97.

Lee, J., Lee, S., Lee, S. J., Kim, D. (2020). Enhancing teachers' cultural competence through a professional development program: A quasi-experimental study. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 94, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103103>

Lengnick-Hall, M. L., Beck, T. E. (2019). Developing industry-education partnerships in emerging fields: Lessons learned from health informatics. *Journal of Vocational Education Training*, 71(1), 1-22. doi: 10.1080/13636820.2018.1541562

Lim, C. P., Zhang, Y. (2019). Introduction to the special issue on technology-enhanced education in the Asia-Pacific region. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 67(2), 237-240. doi: 10.1007/s11423-019-09691-8

Lim, C. P., Chai, C. S. (2018). Examining pre-service teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) trajectories in a design and technology education programme. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 46(4), 411-425.

Lim, E. D., de Guzman, A. B. (2020). Industry-academe partnership in entrepreneurship education among technology and livelihood education teachers. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(1), 26-32.

Lin, C. H., Tsai, C. C. (2018). Differentiated instruction improves students' learning in technology and livelihood education. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 28(4), 1059-1073.

Liu, J., Duan, X., Li, X., Zhang, S. (2018). The effectiveness of collaborative learning for improving learning outcomes in STEM courses. *Higher Education Studies*, 8(1), 1-9. doi: 10.5539/hes.v8n1p1

Llorin, I. J., Albia, J. C. (2019). Collaborative Learning as a Tool in Enhancing Teamwork and Communication Skills of Senior High School Students. *Philippine Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2(2), 43-54.

Lumby, J., Foskett, N. (2021). Leadership in education: An overview. In J. Lumby N. Foskett (Eds.), *The Routledge international handbook of educational leadership and social (in)justice* (pp. 1-11).

Magsino, A. M., Sarmiento, P. L. (2019). Effective Pedagogy in Technical-Vocational Education: A Qualitative Inquiry of Trainers' Beliefs and Practices. *Journal of Technical Education*, 1(1), 48-57.

Madelo, C. C. (2020). Technology-based teaching strategies in technology and livelihood education (TLE): An assessment of their effect on student engagement. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), 1-12.

Manrique, E. G., Jiménez, L. A. G., Padilla, M. S. (2019). Reflective teaching practices and their effects on student learning outcomes: Evidence from a Mexican university. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(35), 77-87.

Maor, D., Tannenbaum, R. (2018). Face-to-face and online learning in TLE: Blending pedagogies for effective teaching. *Journal of Vocational Education Training*, 70(3), 397-414. doi: 10.1080/13636820.2018.1431404

Medina, M. A., Lucero, E. A. (2019). Industry linkage of technology and livelihood education program in Philippine secondary schools. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 9(3), 109-114.

Mendoza, A. B., Malunes, A. J. (2021). Active learning strategies in technology and livelihood education: An analysis of student perceptions and outcomes. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(1), 143-152.

Mishra, P., Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017-1054.

Mulder, R. H., van der Veen, J. T. (2020). The effectiveness of real-world learning experiences in secondary vocational education: A review. *Educational Research Review*, 30, 100323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2020.100323>

Nguyen, D. T., Nguyen, T. M. H. (2020). Industry-academic partnership in curriculum development for computer science education. *Education Sciences*, 10(12), 352.

Pacoma, J. M., Bautista, J. R. (2021). The effectiveness of feedback on the performance of grade 10 students in technology and livelihood education. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 16(4), 2409-2414.

Packer, K. (2020). Understanding and promoting cultural competence in schools. *Journal of School Health*, 90(1), 58-63.

Pelonio, A. M. A., Padoa, L. E. (2020). Industry partnership and technical skills development of technology and livelihood education teachers. *Journal of Technical Education*, 7(1), 44-52.

Quiatchon, J. R., Ozoa, A. L., Quiatchon, J. L. (2018). Integrating technology in technology and livelihood education: Its effect on students' performance. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (UAE)*, 7(4), 126-130.

Rambe, P., Bere, A. (2019). Mobile learning and technology integration in teaching and learning Technology and Livelihood Education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 19.

Rashid, M., Asghar, H. M. (2019). Project-based learning in TLE: Developing 21st century skills. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 14(5), 36-52. doi: 10.3991/ijet.v14i05.9245

Razon, N. A. (2019). Assessment literacy of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) teachers in the Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 39(1), 53-68. doi: 10.1080/02188791.2018.1542314

Rivas, E. C., Japitana, A. E. (2020). Technical Vocational Education and Training Teachers' Understanding of Pedagogical Content Knowledge in the Philippines. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 12(2), 37-46.

Rodriguez, R. F., Diaz, E. M. (2019). The Effect of Collaborative Learning on Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving Skills of Senior High School Students. *International Journal of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Research*, 5(2), 34-43.

Salvaña, R. C., Abao, J. M. V. (2020). Educational Technology Integration in Technology and Livelihood Education: A Perspective from the Philippines. *Journal of Technical Education*, 1(2), 12-21.

Sarmiento, R. G., Atanante, R. A. (2020). Active learning and self-directed learning as tools for developing lifelong learning skills among technology and livelihood education students. *Journal of Research in Technical Education and Training*, 4(1), 14-23.

Saunders, K. T., Zhang, L., Zhao, H. (2020). Industry engagement and university-industry partnerships: The role of intermediaries. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 82(4), 285-307. doi: 10.1504/IJTM.2020.108563

Saunders, M., Welsh, E. (2020). Advocacy for vocational education and training: A review of literature. *Journal of Vocational Education Training*, 72(3), 305-323.

Schulte, C. M., Mann, E. L., Young, J. L. (2019). Teacher leadership in vocational education: A review of the literature. *Journal of Vocational Education Training*, 71(1), 55-76.

Sharma, V., Srivastava, P. R. (2021). Role of industry-academia collaboration in developing skills: A study of engineering institutes in India. *Journal of Education and Work*, 34(1), 87-103. doi: 10.1080/13639080.2019.1703752

Sharma, V., Srivastava, P. R. (2021). Enhancing industry-academia collaboration for skills development in India: An empirical study of engineering institutes. *Journal of Education and Work*, 34(2), 167-185. doi: 10.1080/13639080.2019.1703753

Shiel, G., Martin, R., Forrest, L. (2020). Advocacy in career and technical education: A systematic review of the literature. *Career and Technical Education Research*, 45(2), 119-139.

Shively, K., Rowland, B., Tucker, C. (2020). Augmented reality in TLE: Examining the effects of augmented reality technology on student engagement, motivation, and achievement. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 52(4), 369-382. doi: 10.1080/15391523.2020.1735149

Shroff, R. H., Patel, V. K. (2020). The Impact of Pedagogical Knowledge on Technology Integration in Technical Education. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*,

30(3), 505-523.

Silvano, K. R. E., Reyes, P. F. (2019). Reflective practice as a pedagogical tool for technology and livelihood education teachers. *The Online Journal of New Horizons in Education*, 9(2), 76-87.

Sobremonte, A. A., Guzman, A. B. (2021). The impact of teacher cultural competence on student achievement: A systematic review. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 22(1), 23-32.

Song, D., Lee, J. (2021). A study on the effects of real-world problem-based learning on problem-solving ability and academic achievement in the TLE curriculum. *Sustainability*, 13(12), 6634. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126634>

Sori, A., Suviste, R. (2019). Teacher Professional Development in Technology Education: A Review. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 7(3), 191-203.

Stiggins, R. J. (2007). Assessment through the student's eyes. *Educational Leadership*, 64(8), 22-26. Wolf, A. (2011). Review of vocational education – The Wolf Report. Department for Education. Retrieved from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/100031/2011.pdf

Sun, Y., Wang, Y., Li, X. (2020). Promoting technical and non-technical skills development through collaborative learning in engineering education. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 109(4), 598-623. doi: 10.1002/jee.20308

Wu, P. Y., Wu, M. S., Lin, C. C. (2019). The effect of differentiated instruction on vocational high school students' learning effectiveness and career exploration. *Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 28(1), 25-33.